

contrast microscope for counting symbionts.

The symbionts were counted from the 5 squares (each 1 mm²) of the hemocytometer. Symbionts per insect was calculated and expressed per mg body weight as follows: Symbionts = $a(x+m)/n.v$, where a = symbionts in a known volume of homogenate, m = weight of insects homogenized, n = number of insects homogenized, v = volume of homogenate sampled in the hemocytometer, and x = volume of saline solution used to homogenize nymphs. The experiment was replicated four times.

A second experiment (see table) used 30-d-old IR20 plants sprayed with various neem preparations with untreated plants as controls. Treated and control plants were infested with 30 4-d-old nymphs/replication. Nymphal mortality was recorded 4 and 8 d after treatment. Surviving individuals were removed and homogenized to count endosymbionts.

The YLS population was significantly smaller in BPH that fed on neem-treated IR20 plants than on untreated ones (see

Effect of neem seed derivatives on survival and body weight of fifth-instar BPH nymphs and YLS they harbor.^a

Treatment ^b	Mortality ^c (%)	Body wt (mg/nymph)	YLS (x10 ⁴ /nymph)
<i>Experiment I</i>			
NO 3%	14 b	1.05 a	24.72 a
NO:CAO (2:1)	18 ab	1.12 a	27.45 a
NSKE 5%	80 a	1.02 a	24.91 a
NCE 10%	63 c	1.12 a	27.42 a
NCU (basal)	67 c	1.16 a	31.08 a
Control (untreated)	–	1.42 b	40.35 b
<i>Experiment II</i>			
NO 3%	86 a	1.10 ab	20.95 ab
NO:CAO (2:1)	83 a	1.07 ab	19.63 ab
NSKE 5%	84 a	0.93 a	17.21 a
NCE 10%	15 b	1.09 ab	21.04 ab
NSB (2500 ppm)	66 c	1.38 b	26.80 b
Control (untreated)	–	1.88 c	42.32 c

^aWithin an experiment, means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Each treatment was replicated four times. ^bNO = neem oil, NO:CAO = neem oil:custard-apple oil (vol/vol), NSKE = neem seed kernel extract, NCE = neem cake extract, NCU = neem cake-coated urea, NSB = neem seed bitters. ^cCorrected mortality recorded when nymphs were 12 d old.

table). This decrease could be due to direct antibiotic effect of neem's active principals on the endosymbionts or indirectly through BPH fat bodies which store YLS. Insect brains and fat bodies are highly sensitive to triterpenoid azadirachtin, the principal bitter

component in neem.

Nymphs developing on treated plants weighed less than those on control plants. Nymph mortality was significantly higher on treated plants than on controls, mainly because of molting impairments. □

A new tarsonemid mite, *Ogmotarsonemus* sp. (Tarsonemidae: Acari), on rice in Tamil Nadu, India

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In a survey of phytophagous mites, brown discoloration and necrosis were noted in rice leaf sheaths near ground level. Investigation revealed a tarsonemid mite *Ogmotarsonemus* sp. infestation at all development stages.

Eggs are almost round, transparent, and in clusters. Nymphs are translucent to light white, found between sheaths and culms and inside sheaths. They are oblong with two pairs of legs in the anterior propodosoma and one pair in the metapodosoma. They move sluggishly, staying in the necrotic area even when disturbed.

Adults are light brown with four pairs of legs, more sclerotized, and quite active. Females are oblong; males are broader, with characteristic flange-like enlargement in the femorogenu of the fourth leg.

The first species described under this genus is *Ogmotarsonemus erepsis* Lindquist (1986), attacking *Spartina* sp., a saltmarsh grass in Georgia, United States. This species on rice is new, and is being described for publication elsewhere. □

Neem for control of rice thrips

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We evaluated neem products for thrip control in late sornavari in rice planted in Jun-Jul 1987 in Chengalpattu district.

Rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) can damage leaves in nursery plants and in the young transplanted crop. The randomized block design had three replications using variety TM8089. When incidence was severe, neem products and chemical insecticides (standard checks) were applied at 20 d

Effect of neem products on rice thrips at Chengalpattu, India, 1987.

Treatment	Rate	Thrips ^a (no./sweeps) 2 DAT
Neem seed extract	5%	24.5 bc
Neem seed extract	10%	19.5 ab
Neem cake extract	5%	34.6 c
Neem cake extract	10%	32.1 bc
Neem oil	2%	7.5 a
Phosphamidon 100 EC	250 ml/ha	11.2 a
Fenthion 100 EC	500 ml/ha	6.6 a
Untreated control	–	96.3 d

^aMean of 3 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level based on LSD value. DAT = days after treatment.